

CJPC 2026 VOL.3 (1):56- 65

10.5281/zenodo.20829944

From Stigma to Support: Intergenerational Changes in Attitudes toward Mental Health and Support Systems in Sri Lanka

B.M.A.T. Anupama

Unit of Psychology, Department of Philosophy, University of Kelaniya

Email: thilinianupama99@gmail.com

Abstract

This research explores the differences in mental health help-seeking attitudes and behaviors among three different generations in Sri Lanka, a context shaped by collectivist values and swiftly evolving access to information. Although existing studies highlight increasing awareness, there is lack of understanding of how generational attitudes changes with gender and contemporary support pathways with relation to socio-cultural context of Sri Lanka. Therefore, this study is aimed to explore how attitudes toward mental health related to stigma and support systems differ among Generation X, Generation Y and Generation Z in the Sri Lankan Context. The study employed a qualitative research design and the participants were recruited using purposive sampling by sharing a flyer in social media platforms asking for voluntary participants. Twelve participants were recruited taking four participants from each generation balanced by gender. Semi-structured interviews were conducted to gather data and later analyzed utilizing Braun and Clarke's six-step thematic analysis. Four overarching themes were identified and it showed the distinct mindsets of three generations. The first theme, "Silenced Struggles" reflects the stigma and avoidance behaviors of Generation X while the second theme, "Negotiating Change" indicates the partial acceptance alongside lingering worries about social judgement of Generation Y. The third theme, "Digital Openness" showcases proactive help-seeking via professional services and openly discuss about mental health concerns on digital platforms relevant to Generation Z. The fourth theme, "Barriers, Trust and System Navigation" captures cross generational challenges related to access, affordability and confidence in support systems. Gender norms seem to influence emotional expression and service use, particularly among older generations. Findings highlight the shift from stigma-based avoidance to varied openness to mental healthcare while implying the necessity for more culturally sensitive, generation-specific and gender responsive interventions to improve psychological help seeking in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: *Generational differences, Help-seeking, Mental Health, Stigma, Sri Lanka*

Introduction

Mental health is progressively acknowledged as an essential element of public health; nevertheless, stigma and socio-cultural beliefs still influence how people perceive distress and seek treatment. The literature consistently emphasize that culturally social stigma related to mental health is prevalent in Sri Lanka where negative attitudes lead to individuals to be marginalized in society (Deivanayagam et al., 2024). Individuals might encounter personal, social, relational or structural barriers to help seeking including stigma, lack of awareness, denial, fear of societal repercussions and financial constraints (Deivanayagam et al., 2024). A lack of investment in historical contexts has worsened these issues, with just 1.6% of overall health expenditures dedicated to mental health. It has remained stagnant like that since 2012 (Dimuthu, 2025).

In collectivist societies, where social harmony is valued, individuals tend to conceal personal issues and only turn to professional mental health services as a final option since seeking external support might be perceived as a failure in family (Karasz et al., 2019). These factors have led to hiding psychological issues and postponing help seeking. Research from Sri Lanka indicates that stigma is positively correlated explaining 23% of the variance in treatment delays (Fernando et al., 2016). In the recent years, significant changes influenced urbanization, education and digital connectivity may be transforming perspectives among generations. Urbanization has made individuals more prone to stress related and mood disorders while evolving lifestyles, shifting roles and decline of community support systems have heightened this susceptibility making mental health awareness and stigma reduction crucial (Kathriarachchi et al., 2019).

Generational cohorts commonly defined as Generation X (1965-1980), Generation Y/Millennials (1981-1996) and Generation Z (1997-2012) have encountered distinct socio-cultural surroundings. These differences can affect mental health literacy, perceived stigma and support preferences. Multiple studies indicate that younger generations possess greater mental health literacy which allows them to more effectively recognize signs and symptoms of mental disorders with the advancements of technology (Baral et al., 2022). In South Asian contexts, gender norms often mandate emotional restraint for men and relational obligations for women, potentially influencing disclosure and the use of services in different ways (Ullah, 2025). A study conducted on Sri Lankan university undergraduates revealed that males demonstrate a higher degree of mental health stigma compared to females along with additional obstacles such as hesitance to discuss issues, self-reliance and mistrust of counsellors (Chandrasekara, 2020). In collectivist South Asian cultures, a focus on family harmony and conventional gender roles may inhibit emotional expression in females and younger family members, resulting in unarticulated stress and an increased prevalence of somatization (Karasz et al., 2019).

The current literature highlights a rise in awareness and a decline in stigma among younger individuals, in addition to the expanding influence of online resources and tele-mental health. Statistics show that younger age groups like Generation Z (Gen Z) and Generation Y (Millennials) are significantly more inclined than other demographics to utilize telehealth for mental health sessions, indicating that technological proficiency provides a benefit in obtaining care (Jessel, 2024). Western research further indicates that younger

individuals are more inclined than older generations to pursue mental health resources via social media or online self-help applications (Beecroft, 2025). Nonetheless, there is scarce qualitative evidence from Sri Lanka investigating how generational changes interact with gender to influence specific help seeking pathways encompassing family, friends, religious figures, professional support and online platforms. In Sri Lanka's mental health framework, individuals have the freedom to seek help from any kind of healer, with many moving towards urban centers and private services while others turn to traditional or religious healers if initial treatments fall short of recovery (Mendis, 2004). Qualitative research conducted with community mental health workers in Sri Lanka has revealed a deep trust in traditional beliefs and healers as well as unfavorable views on mental illness and generally inadequate health seeking behaviours (Samarasekare et al., 2012).

Despite the increasing amount of evidence regarding mental health stigma and service use in Sri Lanka, considerable gaps still exist in the literature. Most existing research is quantitative and primarily concentrates on clinical groups, distinct diagnoses or certain demographic subgroups such as university students or perinatal women rather than examining stigma and help seeking across generations in Sri Lankan context. Although there is growing qualitative research on the gendered aspects of mental health in Sri Lanka, this work has primarily focused on specific groups such as survivors of violence, thereby neglecting the wider intersection of gender and help seeking unexplored (Palfreyman et al., 2024).

This study is further informed by Corrigan's Stigma Framework (Corrigan, 2004), which conceptualizes mental health stigma as a multidimensional process involving public

stigma, self-stigma, prejudice, discrimination, and their influence on help-seeking behaviours. The framework suggests that negative societal attitudes toward mental illness may become internalized by individuals, leading to concealment of psychological distress and avoidance of professional support. In the Sri Lankan context, where collectivist cultural values and concerns regarding social reputation remain influential, stigma may shape how different generations perceive mental health difficulties and engage with available support systems. The framework provides a useful lens for understanding how generational differences in stigma influence openness toward mental health discussions, willingness to seek support, and trust in formal and informal sources of care.

This study therefore addresses a significant empirical and methodological gap by utilizing a qualitative research design to explore how Generation X, Generation Y and Generation Z navigate perceived stigma, preferred sources of support and barriers and facilitators to care with relevance to gender in the Sri Lankan context.

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative exploratory approach was utilized to gather subtle meanings and lived experiences related to mental health and help seeking. Qualitative research is becoming acknowledged as an essential methodology strategy in mental health studies, especially since mental health experiences are intrinsically complex, fluid and influenced by culture involving profoundly subjective processes like identity formation, stigma navigation and relational turmoil that cannot easily be simplified into fixed variables or universal measures (Beg, 2025).

This method is particularly effective for exploring socially constructed phenomena and

practices specific to contexts, where the goal is to achieve depth of understanding rather than wide ranging measurement. A qualitative exploratory design is especially suitable when the aim is to comprehend participants' perceived experiences and subjective beliefs regarding phenomena as they navigate their lives (Ellis and Hart, 2023). Due to the scarce qualitative evidence on intergenerational and gendered help seeking and mental health related attitudes in Sri Lanka, an exploratory approach keeps the research relevant insights that may guide future interventions and policy formulation. In this framework, the interpretivist perspective views mental health as a dynamic, socially embedded phenomenon rather than a static diagnostic label (Beg, 2025).

Participants and Sampling

Twelve participants were recruited through purposive sampling, representing three generational cohorts (four from each group) with balanced gender representation (six males and six females). This expanded sample allowed for more detailed comparisons both within and between generational groups while maintaining the depth of qualitative investigation. Inclusion criteria included being a resident of Sri Lanka, participants' age being consistent with generational cohorts mentioned and their willingness to share their views on mental health and help seeking voluntarily. In addition to that, participants who were fluent in either Sinhala or English were recruited as an inclusion criteria. Participants who are currently experiencing severe distress due to any mental health conditions were excluded since sharing these experience as they go through it currently may cause them further distress.

Data Collection

Semi structured interviews were conducted in Sinhala or English depending on the fluency of each participant following an interview protocol that addressed comprehension of mental health, perceived stigma, any previous help seeking experiences, preferred sources of support and their perspectives on tele mental health or digital mental health. Interviews took 30 to 40 minutes and were recorded with the consent of participants. After that, the interviews were transcribed verbatim and Sinhala transcripts were translated into English while ensuring the meanings were maintained.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed utilizing Braun and Clarke's (2006) six step thematic analysis: getting familiarized with data, creating initial codes, identifying themes, reviewing emergent themes, defining and labeling themes and generating the final report. The procedure started with multiple readings of transcripts to attain a thorough understanding of the data. Coding was inductive, enabling themes to arise naturally from participant narratives instead of being dictated by prior theoretical models. Codes were systematically grouped into potential themes, which were then progressively adjusted to guarantee internal consistency within themes and distinct differences among them. This flexible yet rigorous approach was ideally suited for examining the socially embedded and context-dependent aspects of mental health attitudes and help seeking behaviors across three different generations.

Reflexivity

The researcher acknowledges that personal experiences, academic training in psychology, and prior engagement with mental health advocacy may influence the interpretation of participants' narratives. Throughout the research process, reflexive journaling was used to document assumptions, emerging interpretations, and potential biases. Efforts were made to remain attentive to participants' perspectives and to ensure that themes emerged inductively from the data rather than being shaped by pre-existing expectations. Regular review of coding decisions was undertaken to enhance transparency and credibility.

Ethical Considerations

All participants provided informed consent and they were made well aware of the nature and the purpose of the study before data collection. Participants were further made aware that they could withdraw at any moment and can skip questions if they do not feel comfortable to continue. Delicate subjects were handled with caution and information on freely available

mental health support services was given along with the information sheet in case if they need any assistance. Pseudonyms were used to ensure anonymity and any identifying information was eliminated. The recordings were deleted from the device after transcribing them and data was transferred to a password protected file to maintain confidentiality.

Results

Four overarching themes were captured relevant to intergenerational and gendered patterns in attitudes toward mental health and support systems. The sample size of 12 enabled a more thorough investigation of generational variations and strengthened thematic consistency. Illustrative quotes are included under each theme with pseudonyms to preserve the voices of participants. Similar patterns were recognized in each generation implying how generational changes appear with relevance to mental health attitudes and support systems in Sri Lanka. Table 1 provides a summary of the themes and associated subthemes that emerged from the analysis.

Table 1: Summary of the Themes and Associated Subthemes

Theme	Subthemes
Theme 1: Silenced Struggles	Mental health as a private matter; emotional suppression; reliance on religion; fear of social judgement
Theme 2: Negotiating Change	Growing awareness; selective disclosure; cautious acceptance; lingering stigma
Theme 3: Digital Openness	Peer discussions; online information seeking; acceptance of counselling; digital support platforms
Theme 4: Barriers, Trust and System Navigation	Affordability concerns; confidentiality concerns; uncertainty about services; trust issues

Theme 1: Silenced Struggles

Among the four participants from Generation X, mental health was consistently viewed as a private matter that carries stigma. Participants expressed a significant cultural pressure to endure sufferings quietly, frequently associating emotional difficulties with weakness or failure. They seem to be hesitant to openly share their mental health struggles due to stigma around mental health compared to the other two generations' participants. The below given words from participants' narratives further provide evidence for this theme.

“In our time, talking about mental health was considered almost shameful. Usually it was difficult to openly share our struggles as society expected us to be strong no matter what.” (P1, male, Gen X)

“If someone says they are mentally struggling, others immediately think that something is wrong with them.” (P2, female, Gen X)

Male participants emphasized self-reliance and emotional suppression through their narratives

while females expressed their distress highlighting competing family responsibilities due to gender norms.

“Men should not normally show these things. So that we try to solve our problems quietly.” (P3, male, Gen X)

“Even if I feel mentally tired, I cannot stop or take a rest. Family comes first.” (P4, female, Gen X)

All the four accounts of Generation X's participants highlighted that they would normally seek help from religion first and only seek professional help in case of an extreme situation. Overall, this theme reflects how their deeply internalized stigma impacts delayed help seeking and their tendency to silently struggle instead of openly sharing their mental health concerns.

Theme 2: Negotiating Change

Generation Y individuals showed a transitional outlook indicating both increased awareness and persistent stigma. Participants recognized that mental health conversations are now more

transparent but social stigma continues to be problematic.

“Nowadays it’s more accepted than in the past, yet not entirely I guess. People are still careful about who they talk to.” (P5, female, Gen Y)

Female participants demonstrated higher levels of emotional openness while males still showed tendency towards selective disclosure.

“I feel comfortable talking about these issues with my close friends and they even suggest trying counselling if needed.” (P6, female, Gen Y)

“I don’t openly talk about my mental health struggles. Maybe only to one trusted person.” (P8, male, Gen Y)

Overall, this theme reflects how Generation Y is in a transitional standpoint where they shift toward acceptance while still being constrained by stigma.

Theme 3: Digital Openness

Generation Z (Gen Z) participants exhibited the most progressive attitudes toward mental health and support systems characterized by openness, normalization and various channels for help seeking. Mental health was frequently discussed with peers and they seem to consider it to be crucial component of overall well-being compared to the older generations. Below given quotes of their narratives aptly prove this. Participants further disclosed that they actively engage in digital platforms for support and digital platforms help to increase their awareness of mental health concerns.

“We normally share these things with our friends, especially when we go through a rough patch.” (P9, female, Gen Z)

“When I feel stressed, I usually search it online and read about it. It helps me to understand what I am feeling” (P10, male, Gen Z)

Gender differences were less pronounced among Generation Z participants and they appear to be positively viewing support systems as well.

“Even guys talk openly now. There are platforms where you can share your concerns anonymously as well. So even if you hesitate to share openly, now you can still converse about it and get help.” (P11, male, Gen Z)

“We have counselling services at university and students do reach them now. Even at some workplaces, they have these facilities nowadays.” (P12, female, Gen Z)

However, some of them expressed their concerns about reliability of online content as well since there are both correct and misleading information available on certain digital platforms.

“Not everything on the internet is accurate. It can be confusing sometimes because there is a lot of info.” (P11, male, Gen Z)

This theme showcases a significant difference between Generation Z and other two generations when it comes to their openness and less hesitant nature of reaching support systems.

Theme 4: Barriers, Trust and System Navigation

Across all generations, participants noted both structural and psychological barriers that affect the help seeking behaviours such as expenses, lack of awareness about available services and worries regarding confidentiality and effectiveness. They often voiced confusion regarding how to access appropriate services.

“Even if I feel like getting help, I don’t know which service is reliable.” (P8, male, Gen Y)

“How can we trust them with all our private details? Are they trust-worthy? I have that doubt always.” (P2, female, Gen X)

“Counselling is helpful but it’s not easy to afford private sessions regularly.” (P6, female, Gen Y)

This theme reflects how individuals still face several obstacles although they try to seek help for their mental health concerns and this can be seen across all the participants from the three generations considered for the study.

Overall, the findings indicate a distinct generational shift in attitudes on mental health transitioning from stigma and silence to increased openness and variety in help seeking behaviours. Simultaneously, overarching barriers concerning access, trust and system navigation persist in shaping help seeking behaviours across all demographics. Collectively, these themes emphasize the intricate interaction between cultural, generational and structural influences on mental health experiences in Sri Lanka.

Discussion

The present study uncovered four interconnected themes demonstrating how generational differences, gender norms and systemic factors.

The theme, “Silenced Struggles” highlights the profound stigma within Generation X where psychological distress is often concealed and dealt in solitude. This correlates with studies suggesting that in collectivist South Asian cultures, a focus on family cohesion and conventional gender roles can inhibit emotional expression resulting in unvoiced stress (Karasz et al., 2019). Male participants displayed greater emotional suppression aligning with traditional

masculine norms that discourage openness compared to females.

“Negotiating Change” reflects that transitional status of Generation Y who display heightened awareness along with ongoing stigma. Studies indicate that enhancing mental health literacy might influence public perceptions regarding help seeking and support systems more significantly than the actual act of help seeking itself (Yang et al., 2024). This tension was visible among Millennial participants. Concerns regarding confidentiality and trust with possible sources of assistance continued to be significant obstacles as females exhibit higher readiness to share them than males do (Gulliver et al., 2010).

“Digital Openness” emphasizes an important transformation within Generation Z, marked by the normalization of conversations about mental health and interaction with digital support systems. Social media has contributed to greater transparency in conversations about mental health concerns among youth, likely diminishing stigma and promoting the pursuit of treatment (Crossier, 2024). Reduced gender differences in this generational cohort indicate a slow weakening of traditional emotional constraints.

The fourth theme, “Barriers, Trust and System Navigation” highlights common difficulties faced by all generations such as expenses, lack of awareness of available services and concerns regarding confidentiality and professional expertise. Stigma, confidentiality concerns and limited accessibility have consistently been identified as significant obstacles to seeking help among various age groups (Gulliver et al., 2010). The growing reliance on digital platforms also raise worries about false information and trustworthiness on online resources.

Implications

The results emphasize the necessity for multi-level interventions tailored to each generational cohort. Awareness initiatives rooted in the community are crucial for Generation X while making services more accessible, affordable and confidential might effectively involve Generation Y. For Generation Z, combining evidence based digital resources with formal services seem to improve both outreach and trustworthiness. In all generational cohorts, it is essential to implement gender-sensitive strategies to tackle ongoing disparities in emotional expression and the willingness to seek help.

Limitations and Recommendations for Future Studies

This study is constrained by its qualitative design and relatively small sample, restricting generalizability. Reliance on self-reported personal experiences could also create bias. Future studies ought to utilize larger, more varied samples along with mixed-methods approaches to investigate how attitudes convert into real help-seeking actions. Further exploration of digital mental health interventions within the Sri Lankan context is also warranted.

References

Baral, S.P., Prasad, P. and Raghuvamshi, G. (2022) 'Mental health awareness and generation gap', *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, 64(Suppl 3), p. S636. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5545.341859>

Beecroft, W. (2025) 'Gen Z vs. Millennial mental health', *MI Blue Daily*, 13 June. Available at: <https://www.bcbsm.mibluedaily.com/stories/health-and-wellness/gen-z-vs-millennial-mental-health>

Beg, M.J. (2025) 'Qualitative methods in mental health research: standards for ethical inquiry, research practice, and peer review', *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/02537176251363817>

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77–101. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>

Chandrasekara, W.S. (2020) 'Beyond stigma: perceived barriers and enablers for help seeking for mental health issues in undergraduate students in Sri Lanka', *Engineering Social Transformation through Research & Development*. Available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342926145>

Crosier, S. (2024) 'Gen Z, social media, and mental health', *Emory University - Rollins School of Public Health*, 22 May. Available at: <https://sph.emory.edu/news/gen-z-social-media-mental-health>

Dimuthu, I. (2025) 'Critical review: Sri Lanka's mental health crisis – underfunding, stigma, and service gaps', *Centre for Research - National Hospital Kandy*, 31 May. Available at: <https://c4rnhk.org/critical-review-sri-lankas-mental-health-crisis-underfunding-stigma-and-service-gaps/>

Ellis, J. and Hart, D. (2023) 'Strengthening the choice for a generic qualitative research design', *The Qualitative Report*, 28(6), pp. 1759–1768. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2023.5474>

Fernando, S.M., Deane, F.P. and McLeod, H.J. (2016) 'The delaying effect of stigma on mental health help-seeking in Sri Lanka', *Asia-Pacific Psychiatry*, 9(1), p. E12255. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/appy.12255>

Gulliver, A., Griffiths, K.M. and Christensen, H. (2010) 'Perceived barriers and facilitators to mental health help-seeking in young people: a systematic review', *BMC Psychiatry*, 10(1).

Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244x-10-113>

Jessel, N. (2024) 'Gen-Z and millennials struggle most with mental health', *Athenahealth*.

Available at:

<https://www.athenahealth.com/resources/blog/tel-ehealth-care-coordination-to-address-mental-health-crisis>

Karasz, A., Gany, F., Escobar, J., Flores, C., Prasad, L., Inman, A., Kalasapudi, V., Kosi, R., Murthy, M., Leng, J. and Diwan, S. (2019) 'Mental health and stress among South Asians', *Journal of Immigrant and Minority Health*, 21(S1), pp. 7–14. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10903-016-0501-4>

Kathriarachchi, S., Seneviratne, V.L. and Amarakoon, L. (2019) 'Development of mental health care in Sri Lanka: lessons learned', *Taiwanese Journal of Psychiatry*, 33(2), p. 55.

Available at:

https://doi.org/10.4103/tpsy.tpsy_15_19

Mendis, N. (2004) 'Mental health services in Sri Lanka', *International Psychiatry*, 1(3), p. 10.

Available at:

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6733103/>

Palfreyman, A., Vijayaraj, K., Riyaz, S., Rizwan, Z., Sivayokan, S., Thenakoon, T.H.S., Dayabandara, M., Hanwella, R. and Devakumar, D. (2024) 'What women want: mental health in the context of violence against women in Sri Lanka — a qualitative study of priorities and capacities for care', *Violence Against Women*.

Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1177/10778012241230326>

Samarasekare, N., Lloyd, M., Davies, M. and Siribaddana, S. (2012) 'The stigma of mental illness in Sri Lanka: the perspectives of community mental health workers', *Stigma Research and Action*, 2(2), pp. 93–99. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5463/SRA.v1i1.13>

Deivanayagam, T.A., Ní Chobhthaigh, S., Devakumar, D., Patel, K. and Rannan-Eliya, R.P. (2024) 'Mental health prevalence, healthcare use and access between 2018 and 2022 in Sri Lanka: an analysis of survey data', pp. 1–16. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.3310/hjwa5078>

Ullah, S.S. (2025) 'Impact of gender role expectations on mental health among working women in South Asian households', *Journal of Social Science Perspectives*, 2(1), pp. 1–5. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.65761/jssp.2025.v2.i1.6>

Yang, X., Hu, J., Zhang, B., Ding, H., Hu, D. and Li, H. (2024) 'The relationship between mental health literacy and professional psychological help-seeking behavior among Chinese college students: mediating roles of perceived social support and psychological help-seeking stigma', *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1356435>